

STUDIES ON 3-*o*-TOLYL- AND 3-*p*-TOLYL-2:4-THIAZOLIDIONES

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3-*o*-Tolyl- and 3-*p*-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidiones have been synthesised by condensing the corresponding *S*-di-*o*-tolyl- and *S*-di-*p*-tolylthioureas with monochloroacetic acid in glacial acetic acid medium, and their various derivatives with aldehydes, diazonium chlorides and mercuric acetate have been prepared.

In continuation to the earlier work on 3-aryl-2:4-thiazolidiones (Bhargava and Rao, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 463) and in view of the close relationship between thiazolidiones and thiazolidones and the reported use of thiazolidone compounds as anaesthetics (Surrey, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3354), amoebacidal agents (Surrey and Cutler, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 578) and anticonvulsants (Troutman and Long, *ibid.*, 1948, 70, 3436), it was considered worthwhile to prepare 3-*o*-tolyl- and 3-*p*-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidiones under the conditions laid down by Bhargava and Rao (*loc. cit.*).

The thiazolidiones have been obtained in good yields by the interaction of *S*-di-*p*- and *S*-di-*o*-tolylthioureas with monochloroacetic acid in glacial acetic acid. The reactive methylene group of the compounds has been successfully condensed with aromatic aldehydes, α -nitroso- β -naphthol and aryldiazonium chlorides, forming respectively 5-arylidene-, 5-arylimino- and 5-arylazo-2:4-thiazolidiones. The assumption that the azo group is attached to the thiazolidione nucleus in position-5 is based on the observations of Bogert and Chertcoff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2864; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1924, 10, 418). They obtained dyes by coupling diazotised *p*-nitroaniline and sulphanic acid with 2-aminothiazole, from which they concluded that the azo group was attached to position-5 of the thiazole nucleus. On account of a close relationship among thiazole, thiazolidone and thiazolidione, similar behaviour is also expected of thiazolidiones. Meerwein, Buchner and Engster (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, 162, 237) studied the reactions of diazonium salts with $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl compounds and concluded that the arylazo group entered the position α to the activating carbonyl group. Hence, the attachment of the azo group to -CH₂- group in position-5 in α -position to the activating carbonyl group is justified and is further supported by the observation that when the -CH₂- group in position-5 of the thiazolidione nucleus is blocked by condensation with aromatic aldehydes, no azo dye is formed.

Further, mercuration of 3-*p*-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione (I) with mercuric acetate has yielded 3-acetoxymercuri-*p*-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione (II). The acetoxymercuri group is assumed to enter the aryl nucleus in view of the fact that the 3-*o*-tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione derivatives are mercurated under similar conditions giving rise to exactly similar products. This therefore rules out the possibility of acetoxymercuri group having entered the -CH₂- group in 5-position of the thiazolidione nucleus.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-*p*-Tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione was prepared according to the method of Klare, Markley and Reid (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 2137) in glacial acetic acid or alcohol along with HCl (conc.) in white needles, m.p. 162°. (Found: S, 15.54. C₁₀H₉O₂NS requires S, 15.49 per cent).

3-*O*-Tolyl-2:4-thiazolidione was prepared by the method of Bhargava and Rao (*loc. cit.*), m.p. 154°.

3-*O*-Tolyl-5-benzylidene-2:4-thiazolidione.—A mixture of thiazolidione (0.5 g.) and benzaldehyde (0.3 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.), and fused sodium acetate (1 g.) was heated under reflux for 1½ hours. On pouring the contents into water a precipitate was obtained. After keeping it overnight, the yellow precipitate was filtered off and the product was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid.

Similarly other aldehydes were condensed yielding 5-arylidene derivatives. The properties and analytical data of these derivatives are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

3-*O*-Tolyl-5-arylidene-2:4-thiazolidione.

Aldehyde.	% Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
Benzaldehyde	72	Deep yellow	133-35°	10.86	10.84
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	66	Yellow	156°	9.62	9.41
<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	75	Light yellow	160°	10.38	10.30
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	70	Do	168-70	10.41	10.30
Cinnamaldehyde	60	Yellowish brown	98° (decomp.)		
Furfuraldehyde	55	Greyish brown	101°	11.03	11.22

3-*p*-Tolyl-5-benzylidene-2:4-thiazolidione was prepared according to the above method, and similarly other aldehydes and α -nitroso- β -naphthol were also condensed with the thiazolidione. The products and their analytical data are noted in Table II.

TABLE II

3-*p*-Tolyl-5-arylidene- and -5-arylimino-2:4-thiazolidiones.

Aldehydes or nitroso compound.	% Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Calc.
Benzaldehyde	70	Pale yellow	208°	10.80	10.84
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	80	Yellow	224°	9.46	9.41
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	50	Do	216°	9.42	9.41
<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	82	Pale yellow	222°	10.21	10.30
Salicylaldehyde	62	Do	242°	10.34	10.30
Anisaldehyde	53	Yellow	204°	9.90	9.86
<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde	67	Orange	236°	9.47	9.49
Cinnamaldehyde	45	Yellow	201°	9.94	9.98
Vanillin	77	Do	235°	9.37	9.39
Veratraldehyde.	84	Pale yellow	194°	8.99	9.03
Piperonal	91	Do	220°	9.42	9.45
α -Nitroso- β -naphthol	71	Brown	205°	8.82	8.85

3-*o*-Tolyl-5-phenylazo-2 : -4-thiazolidione was prepared by the method of Bhargava and Goswami (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 763). Similarly the thiazolidione was condensed with a number of aryldiazonium chlorides. The properties of these compounds and their analytical data are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Diazonium chloride of amines.	Colour.	M.P.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.
Aniline	Yellow	148°	10.37	10.30
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	Dirty yellow	136°	9.86	9.84
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Light yellow	146°	10.01	9.84
α -Naphthylamine	Dark brown	119°	8.82	8.86
β -Naphthylamine	Scarlet-red	113-15°	8.87	8.86
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	Ash-grey	145°	8.32	8.38
Sulphanilamide	Deep yellow	120-22°	16.36	16.41

Similarly 5-arylazo derivatives of 3-*p*-tolyl-2 : 4-thiazolidione were prepared (Table IV).

TABLE IV

Diazonium chloride of amines.	Colour.	M.P.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.
Aniline	Brown	130°	10.34	10.30
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Orange-red	195°	9.81	9.84
Sulphanilamide	Scarlet-red	> 300°	16.36	16.41

3-Acetoxymercuri-*p*-tolyl-2 : 4-thiazolidione.—3-*p*-Tolyl-2 : 4-thiazolidione (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) and to this absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) and mercuric acetate (1.5 g.), dissolved in water (15 c.c.) and acidified with acetic acid, were added. On keeping overnight, a precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed respectively with dilute acetic acid, hot water and alcohol. It was crystallised from alcohol in a pale yellow form, m. p. 310°. (Found: Hg, 42.81. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4NSHg$ requires Hg, 43.08 per cent).

3-Acetoxymercuri-*o*-tolyl-5-benzylidene 2 : 4-thiazolidione was prepared by the above method by mercurating 3-*o*-tolyl-5-benzylidene-2 : 4-thiazolidione and was obtained in a yellowish white form, m. p. 170-71°. (Found: Hg, 36.66. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4NSHg$ requires Hg, 36.49 per cent).

The presence of one acetoxymercuri group in this compound and in 3-acetoxymercuri-*o*-tolyl-2 : 4-thiazolidione (Bhargava and Rao, *loc. cit.*) as well as in 3-acetoxymercuri-*p*-tolyl-2 : 4-thiazolidione clearly indicates that the acetoxymercuri group has entered the aryl nucleus at position-3 and not the methylene group at position 5.

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